

1 **Development of an antibacterial coaxial bionanocomposite based on electrospun**
2 **core/shell fibers loaded with ethyl lauroyl arginate and cellulose nanocrystals for**
3 **active food packaging**

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12

13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Developing antimicrobial electrospun bionanocomposites with core/shell structure is an
15 innovative strategy for producing active food packaging materials. The aim of this study was
16 developing an antibacterial electrospun mat based on polylactic acid (PLA) coaxial fibers
17 containing ethyl lauroyl arginate (LAE) and cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) through
18 electrospinning. The effect of the coaxial structure and the incorporation of both components
19 on the structural, thermal and release properties of the electrospun PLA was analyzed. LAE
20 release studies were carried out in 10% and 95% EtOH, and results correlated with
21 antibacterial assays. Structural analysis only indicated some chemical interactions through
22 hydrogen bonding between PLA and LAE in the core structure. The incorporation of LAE
23 and CNC produced a plasticizing effect in the PLA, and the crystallinity of polymer was
24 maintained by the presence of CNC. Core/shell structure and the presence of CNC slowed

25 down the LAE release. Furthermore, the bionanocomposite exhibited strong bactericidal
26 activities.

27 **Keywords:** active packaging; antimicrobial; electrospinning; polylactic acid.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Electrospinning is a simple, scalable, economical and novel technology able to encapsulate
31 active compounds into ultrathin structures denominated “fibers” with a large surface area
32 (Muñoz-Shugulí et al., 2021). This electrodynamic process is based on the application of a
33 voltage to a polymeric solution that produces a jet with a conical structure named “Taylor’s
34 Cone”, where the solvent is evaporated to obtain an electrospun mat composed by the fibers
35 (Velásquez et al., 2021).

36 In the food packaging research area, polylactic acid (PLA) has been one of the most studied
37 bio-derived polymers for developing antimicrobial electrospun materials in the last years.
38 This fact has been due to the growing interest in generating biodegradable packaging
39 materials able to protect food against spoilage and thus, extend their shelf-life. Several
40 compounds, such as carvacrol, ungeremine, thymol, tea polyphenols, among others, have
41 been used due to their good antibacterial properties (Altan et al., 2018; Y. Liu et al., 2018;
42 Min et al., 2021; Moeini et al., 2020). Thus, active compounds have been incorporated into
43 PLA fibers in order to obtain antibacterial electrospun materials. However, varied
44 antibacterial properties have been obtained with such active materials because Gram-
45 positive and Gram-negative bacteria show dissimilar behaviors due to their different cellular
46 structure (cell membrane) (Liu et al., 2018; Radusin et al., 2019). In this context, ethyl
47 lauroyl arginate (LAE) displays an interesting and promising alternative for developing
48 potential antibacterial electrospun materials thanks to its strong antimicrobial activity. This
49 fact has been mainly evidenced because low LAE concentrations ($< 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) have been

50 sufficient for inhibiting the growth of different Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria
51 compared to values obtained with nanoparticles or essential oils (Hajipour et al., 2012; Ma
52 et al., 2020; Van de Vel et al., 2019). LAE is a cationic surfactant derived from lauric acid,
53 L-arginine and ethanol, generally recognized as safe by Food and Drug Administration and
54 authorized as a food preservative by European Food Safety Authority (Ma et al., 2020). This
55 compound has been widely used in the food industry due to its excellent antibacterial
56 properties with low-dose application (Haghighi et al., 2020). Furthermore, some
57 developments of active packaging films and electrospun materials containing LAE have
58 evidenced its great antibacterial property (Higuera et al., 2013; Theinsathid et al., 2012).
59 Nonetheless, maintaining a potent and prolonged antibacterial activity requires a slow
60 release of the active compound to the medium. Regarding electrospun mats, active fibers
61 with uniaxial structure have generally exhibited a burst compound release during the first
62 hours. Against this problem, the development of fibers with a core/shell structure through
63 the coaxial electrospinning technique is a good alternative.

64 Coaxial electrospinning is an innovative technology able to produce core/shell fibers that
65 exhibit several advantages compared to fibers obtained with the traditional technique. One
66 of them is the modification of the release of the encapsulated compound (Lu et al., 2016;
67 Patiño Vidal et al., 2021). In this work, LAE was encapsulated into the core of the fibers in
68 order to slow down its release, and therefore prolong its antimicrobial property.

69 On the other hand, the incorporation of natural nanoparticles as cellulose nanocrystals (CNC)
70 into active materials has been also a novel strategy for slowing down the compounds release.
71 CNC are highly ordered structures obtained from the removal of amorphous regions of the
72 cellulose by mechanical or chemical treatments. Their use in the development of
73 nanocomposite materials has been attributed to their high aspect ratio, low-cost, renewable
74 nature, and their role as reinforcement of physical properties of packaging materials (W.

75 Liu et al., 2018; Sung et al., 2017). Several biodegradable active developments have
76 evidenced improvement of physical and transport properties by adding CNC, such as: i)
77 decrease of the release rate of the active compound to food simulants; ii) decrease of water
78 and oxygen permeability values; and iii) increase of Young's modulus and elongation at
79 break (Gupta et al., 2021; Natarajan et al., 2022; Rojas et al., 2020). Thus, the incorporation
80 of CNC into the shell structure of coaxial fibers would avoid the burst release of LAE and
81 would maintain the effective antibacterial activity of the nanocomposite. The aim of this
82 work was to develop an antibacterial bionanocomposite based on PLA coaxial fibers, whose
83 core and shell were loaded with LAE and CNC, respectively. The effect of incorporating
84 LAE and CNC and the core/shell structure on structural, thermal and release properties of
85 the electrospun PLA was studied. Furthermore, the antibacterial activities of the
86 bionanocomposite against *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Escherichia coli* as Gram(-)
87 bacteria, and *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria innocua* as Gram(+) bacteria were
88 determined.

89

90 **2. Material and methods**

91 *2.1 Polymers, reagents and microorganisms*

92 Polylactic acid 2003D with a specific gravity of 1.24 was obtained from Natureworks®
93 (USA). Cellulose nanocrystals (5-20 nm width and 150-200 nm length) were purchased from
94 the University of Maine. Ethyl lauroyl arginate was supplied by PRINAL (Chile).

95 Solvents, such as chloroform (CHCl₃), dimethylformamide (DMF), trifluoroacetic acid
96 (TFA), ultrapure water and ethanol (EtOH), were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Chile).

97 *Salmonella typhimurium* ATCC 14028 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, as Gram(-)
98 bacteria, and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Listeria innocua* ATCC 33090, as
99 Gram(+) bacteria, were obtained from the Biotechnology and Applied Microbiology

100 Laboratory (USACH, Chile). Microorganisms were maintained in trypticase soy agar (TSA)
101 at 4 °C. For each antibacterial test, a loopful of each strain was transferred to a TSA plate
102 and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h to obtain fresh early-stationary phase cells.

103

104 *2.2 Development of electrospun antibacterial bionanocomposite*

105 A coaxial electrospinning system (Spraybase® power Supply Unit, Ireland) connected to a
106 rotary system collector (4LABS, Chile) was used to obtain a core/shell PLA-LAE/PLA-
107 CNC1 bionanocomposite. 10% (w/v) PLA solutions under a solvent mixture of CHCl₃:DMF
108 at 7:3 volume ratio were used to obtain both core and shell structures. A concentration of
109 LAE at 15 wt% (respect to PLA mass) was incorporated into the core structure in order to
110 afford antibacterial activity (PLA-LAE structure) (*Appendix A in the Supplementary file*
111 *displays the antibacterial activity of LAE – selection criteria of LAE concentration*). On the
112 other hand, CNC at 1 wt% (respect to polymer mass) was incorporated into the PLA shell
113 structure (PLA-CNC1) (*Appendix B in the Supplementary file presents the selection criteria*
114 *of CNC concentration*). Core and shell polymeric solutions were transferred to 10 mL
115 syringes and connected through PTFE tubes to a coaxial device composed of two concentric
116 stainless-steel needles (0.7 and 2.1 mm diameters). External and internal flow rates were
117 0.75 and 1.8 mL h⁻¹, respectively. Electrospinning process parameters used to obtain the
118 electrospun bionanocomposite PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 were: distance between needle tip and
119 collector of 10 cm, roller speed of 500 rpm, a voltage between 13 to 16 kV, and a collecting
120 time of 6.5 h.

121 Furthermore, uniaxial PLA, PLA-LAE and PLA-CNC1 fibers and coaxial PLA-LAE/PLA
122 fiber were also developed in order to study the effect of incorporating LAE and CNC on
123 PLA thermal properties and the morphology of the coaxial fibers, and the presence of CNC
124 on the LAE release. Uniaxial fibers were obtained using a single needle of 0.7 mm diameter

125 and a flow rate of 1.8 mL h⁻¹. Electrospinning parameters were equal to the parameters used
126 for coaxial PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 bionanocomposite. The thickness of resulting electrospun
127 mats were measured by a digital micrometer Mitutoyo ID-C112 and they all maintained a
128 thickness of 50 ± 3 μm.

129

130 *2.3 Characterization of physico-chemical properties of electrospun bionanocomposite*

131 The external morphology and the diameter of the electrospun PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 fibers
132 were observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) TESCAN (VEGA3, Czech
133 Republic). Samples were coated with gold-palladium using Sputtering System Hummer 6.2.
134 SEM micrographs were obtained at 2000x and 10000x magnifications. The diameters of the
135 fibers resulted from 100 measurements carried out with ImageJ v. 1.51 program.

136 The presence of the functional groups of PLA, LAE and CNC, and their interactions in the
137 electrospun bionanocomposite were analyzed through Fourier Transform Infrared
138 Spectrometer (FTIR) Bruker Alpha (IFS 66V, Germany) coupled to a crystal diamond of
139 attenuated total reflection Bruker Platinum. FTIR spectra were obtained in Attenuated Total
140 Reflectance (ATR) mode in a wavenumber range from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ with a resolution
141 of 2 cm⁻¹ and 64 scans. The spectra analyses were performed with the program Opus v. 7.0.

142 The effect of LAE and CNC incorporation on the calorimetric parameters of the PLA fibers
143 was analyzed through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses using a STARE
144 TGA/DSC analyzer (Mettler Toledo GC20, Switzerland). 4-5 mg of each sample were
145 placed into aluminum capsules, and a thermal heating program from 0 to 250 °C at 10 °C
146 min⁻¹ heating rate was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. The glass transition
147 temperature (T_g), cold crystallization temperature (T_{cc}), melting temperature (T_m), and
148 melting (ΔH_m) and cold crystallization (ΔH_{cc}) enthalpies were determined. Furthermore, the
149 crystallinity of PLA (X_c) was calculated through equation 1:

150
$$X_c(\%) = \frac{(\Delta H_m - \Delta H_{cc})}{X_{PLA} \Delta H_{mo}} \quad (1)$$

151 Where ΔH_{m0} is the melting enthalpy of a wholly crystalline polymer (PLA= 93.1 J g⁻¹) and
152 X_{PLA} is the mass fraction of PLA in the fiber (Cerro et al., 2021).

153

154 *2.4 Study of the release kinetics of LAE*

155 Specific migration assays of LAE from the uniaxial and coaxial fibers to 10% and 95%
156 EtOH, as aqueous and fatty food simulants, respectively, were carried out in order to evaluate
157 the mass transfer of this antimicrobial compound from the active electrospun structures.
158 Assays were carried out according to the EU Regulation N° 10/2011 about materials and
159 plastic objects to contact with food (Muñoz-Shugulí et al., 2018; Sepulveda et al., 2020). 3
160 cm² of each electrospun mat (approximately 0.020 ± 0.005 g) were immersed into 5 mL of
161 each simulant (6 dm² L⁻¹ ratio) at 40 °C for 48 h in order to determine the release kinetics of
162 LAE. The amount of released LAE was quantified through high-performance liquid
163 chromatography (HPLC) at 0.08, 0.17, 0.33, 0.67, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 16, 24 and 48 h. Three
164 replicates of each sample were considered, and two vials of each replicate were processed.
165 20 µL of liquid phase was injected in an HPLC chromatograph (Waters Alliance, USA)
166 coupled to a photodiode-array detector Waters PDA 2998 (200 nm was the selected
167 wavelength for LAE quantification) and equipped with a column of reverse phase Waters
168 Symmetry® C18 (5 µm, 3.9 mm x 150 mm). A mobile phase composed of a mixture 50:50
169 acetonitrile and water with 0.1% TFA at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹ was used to detect the
170 active compound (Patiño Vidal et al., 2021). Calibration curves of LAE (from 25 to 200 mg
171 L⁻¹) in both simulants were done in order to quantify the release of LAE.

172 The kinetic process and the extent of release are two important parameters determining the
173 mass transfer phenomenon that occurs when the active compound is released from a

174 polymeric packaging to food (Rojas et al., 2021). The extent of release is determined if the
175 phase equilibrium is reached during the compound release, and it is expressed in terms of
176 the partition coefficient (K) that corresponds to the ratio between compound concentration
177 in the polymeric matrix and in the food simulant ($K=C_{pm}/C_{fs}$). Therefore, K coefficients were
178 determined by the LAE concentration ratio between the polymeric matrix and the food
179 simulant after reaching the plateau value in the cumulative release plot. Meanwhile, the
180 kinetic process that determines the diffusion rate of the compound inside the polymeric
181 matrix to reach the equilibrium is expressed in terms of the diffusion coefficient (D) and
182 defined by Fick's Law (López de Dicastillo et al., 2013). D coefficients were determined by
183 the procedure shown in the *Supplemental File Appendix B.1*.

184

185 2.5. Antibacterial activity of electrospun bionanocomposite

186 The antibacterial activities of the bionanocomposite PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 against Gram (-
187) bacteria *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium* and Gram (+) bacteria *L. innocua* and *S. aureus*, were
188 tested following the International Normative ASTM E2149-13-1. A loopful of each
189 microorganism in stationary phase was transferred to trypticase soy broth (TSB) and
190 incubated at 37 °C until reaching the exponential phase ($\approx 10^7$ CFU mL⁻¹). Later, 100 µL of
191 each bacterial suspension was added to assay tubes with 9.9 mL of phosphate buffer solution
192 to reach a final concentration of 10⁵ CFU mL⁻¹ bacteria. Subsequently, 6 cm² of
193 bionanocomposite was put into the assay tubes to guarantee the area/volume ratio of 6 dm²
194 L⁻¹. The samples were incubated at 37 °C and 150 rpm for 24 h. Subsequently, serial
195 dilutions and growth of these bacterial dilutions on TSA plates at 37 °C for 24 h were done.
196 The experiment was carried out in triplicate. Furthermore, bacterial suspensions without
197 fiber named "CNT-Bacteria" and with non-active PLA fiber named "CNT-PLA" were used

198 as control samples. The antimicrobial activity was expressed as the logarithmic cycle
199 reduction and calculated through equation 2:

$$200 \quad \text{Log}_{10} \text{ bacteria reduction} = \text{Log}_{10} (\text{CNT-PLA}) - \text{Log}_{10} (\text{experimental sample}) \quad (2)$$

201

202 *2.6 Statistical analysis*

203 Results of the release studies, thermal properties and antibacterial activity were statistically
204 analyzed by variance analysis (ANOVA) and Tukey's Test, using the InfoStat program
205 (2008) in order to detect differences between the samples with a confidence level of 95%
206 ($p < 0.05$). The experimental design was random type for three replicates.

207

208 **3. Results and discussions**

209 Electrospun non-active and active fibers with and without core/shell structure resulted on a
210 final concentration of 4.2 wt% of LAE and 0.67 wt% of CNC respect to the electrospun
211 membrane total mass, as is shown in Table S2.

212 *3.1 Morphology of electrospun fibers*

213 The morphology and the diameter of the developed electrospun fibers are shown in Figure
214 1. The PLA fiber presented a diameter of approx. 590 nm and the presence of some beads.
215 However, the incorporation of LAE (PLA-LAE fiber) reduced the formation of beads and
216 narrowed the diameter distribution. This result could be associated with a decrease in the
217 solution viscosity because of its surfactant effect, which has been previously observed in
218 electrospun nanofibers of chitosan/poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) with LAE (Deng et al.,
219 2018). Thus, the electrospinning process was favored with a greater jet stretching, resulting
220 in uniform active fibers with homogeneous diameters (Abutaleb et al., 2017; Shao et al.,
221 2019). Conversely, as Figure 1 shows, the incorporation of CNC produced a decrease in the

222 average diameter of the fibers PLA-CNC1 and the appearance of beads, probably because
 223 the remaining negatively charged CNC sulfate groups increased the electrical conductivity
 224 of the polymeric solution. This fact was recently evidenced by Patel et al. (2020) whose
 225 results revealed the diameter of PLA nanofibers decreased from 300 to 100 nm due to the
 226 incorporation and increase of CNC concentration (Patel et al., 2020).

227
 228 **Figure 1.** SEM micrographs and diameter distribution histogram of electrospun fibers.
 229 Symbol “ \bar{x} ” means average diameter and “ σ ” means standard deviation.

230 Regarding the coaxial fibers, PLA-LAE/PLA displayed an average diameter similar to the
231 uniaxial PLA-LAE fibers but with greater homogeneity of the diameter distribution.
232 Likewise, bead formation was not shown in PLA-LAE/PLA. Similarly, PLA-LAE/PLA-
233 CNC1 fibers presented uniform diameters but with a diameter distribution slightly narrower
234 than PLA-LAE/PLA. Besides, the presence of CNC slightly increased their average diameter
235 compared to the active coaxial fibers without CNC. This result could be associated with a
236 higher amount of mass in the shell because the added CNC concentration was calculated
237 respect to the total PLA mass used for preparing the polymeric solution of such external
238 structure (1 g of PLA + 0.01 g of CNC in 10 mL of a solvent mixture CHCl₃:DMF, see
239 *Section 2.2*).

240

241 *3.2 Structural characterization (ATR-FTIR analysis)*

242 FTIR spectra of the components and uniaxial and coaxial fibers are shown in Figure 2. The
243 CNC spectrum displayed the characteristic bands of these nanoparticles, such as stretching
244 vibration of the hydroxyl groups at 3346 cm⁻¹ and stretching vibration of the -CH₂ groups at
245 2902 cm⁻¹. The presence of adsorbed water in the CNC was verified at 1639 cm⁻¹,
246 corresponding to scissoring vibration by deformation of hydroxyl groups. Scissoring and
247 wagging bending vibrations of -CH₂ groups were evidenced at 1430 and 1318 cm⁻¹, and
248 angular deformation of the C-H bonds at 1373 cm⁻¹. The vibrations of asymmetric stretching
249 of the β-(1-4) glycosidic bonds (C-O-C bonds) and stretching of the C-O bond were shown
250 at 1164 and 1113 cm⁻¹, respectively. The two bands at 1060 and 1034 cm⁻¹ were associated
251 with C-O stretch vibrations in the primary and secondary aliphatic alcohols of the CNC.
252 Furthermore, the symmetric vibration of the C-O-S bonds and the out-of-plane bending
253 vibration of the C-OH were evidenced at 810 and 670 cm⁻¹, respectively (Haghighi et al.,
254 2021; Rasheed et al., 2020).

255 Regarding the LAE spectrum, peaks in the region between 3422 and 3169 cm^{-1} were
 256 associated with the symmetric and asymmetric N-H vibrations of the amino groups. The
 257 asymmetric and symmetric C-H stretching vibrations of the methylene/methyl groups were
 258 observed at 2915 and 2850 cm^{-1} , while the scissoring bending of methylene is shown at 1474
 259 cm^{-1} . The vibration of the carbonyl group was observed at 1755 and 1645 cm^{-1} , and vibration
 260 of the C-O bond of the ester group between 1246 and 1096 cm^{-1} . The signal at 1645 cm^{-1}
 261 was associated with the stretching of the carbonyl group bond of the amide in the LAE
 262 backbone (amide I). Meanwhile, the band at 1527 cm^{-1} was attributed to the combination of
 263 vibrations (amide II), stretching of the C-N bond and scissoring bending of N-H (Chi &
 264 Catchmark, 2017; Haghghi et al., 2020).

265

266 **Figure 2.** FTIR spectra of CNC, LAE, uniaxial fibers of PLA, PLA-CNC and PLA-LAE,
267 and coaxial fiber PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1.

268 The bands of the main functional groups of PLA were displayed in the spectrum of PLA
269 uniaxial fiber. Bands at 2995 and 2944 cm^{-1} were related to symmetric and asymmetric C-H
270 stretching in the $-\text{CH}_3$ groups. The stretching of the carbonyl group and C-O-C bond were
271 observed at 1751 and 1182 cm^{-1} , respectively. Vibrations between 1452 and 1360 cm^{-1} were
272 associated with asymmetric and symmetric bending of the C-H bond in the methyl groups
273 of PLA (Cerro et al., 2021; Min et al., 2021). Bands at 1128, 1084 and 1043 cm^{-1}
274 corresponded to C-O stretching, while bands at 868 and 755 cm^{-1} were associated with the
275 amorphous and crystalline regions of the polymer, respectively (Molinaro et al., 2013).

276 PLA fibers with and without CNC showed similar spectra due to the low concentration of
277 these nanoparticles. Nonetheless, the displacement of the band at 868 cm^{-1} to 871 cm^{-1}
278 revealed changes in the crystalline structure of PLA with CNC incorporation (Arjmandi et
279 al., 2015; Mohamad Haafiz et al., 2015). Meanwhile, some interactions between the polymer
280 and the antimicrobial compound in the PLA-LAE fiber were verified. The shifting of the
281 peak at 1645 cm^{-1} of the LAE to 1651 cm^{-1} in the PLA-LAE fiber showed that the carbonyl
282 group of the amide of LAE possibly interacted through hydrogen bonding with end hydroxyl
283 groups of PLA chains. Similarly, Haghghi et al. (2020) reported that carbonyl, NH_2 , and
284 NH functionalities of LAE contributed to competitive intermolecular interactions with the
285 hydroxyl groups of chitosan-poly(vinyl alcohol) film network through ATR-FTIR analysis.
286 Finally, the FTIR spectrum of the PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 bionanocomposite was similar to
287 PLA-LAE uniaxial fiber, and interactions LAE-PLA were evidenced in both cases.

288

289 *3.3 Thermal properties*

290 DSC parameters and crystallinity of the developed electrospun fibers obtained during the
 291 first heating are shown in Table 1.

292 **Table 1.** DSC parameters and crystallinity of the fibers from the first heating process.

Electrospun fiber	T _g (°C)	T _{cc} (°C)	ΔH _{cc} (J g ⁻¹)	T _m (°C)	ΔH _m (J g ⁻¹)	X _{c,PLA} (%)
PLA	69.2±0.2 ^c	92.9±1.5 ^b	9.4±1.1 ^a	154.4±0.3 ^a	32.2±2.0 ^a	24.3±0.9 ^b
PLA-LAE	61.9±0.1 ^a	88.5±0.2 ^a	12.6±0.3 ^{bc}	155.8±0.2 ^a	29.5±0.6 ^a	18.8±0.4 ^a
PLA-CNC1	61.1±0.0 ^a	102.2±0.1 ^c	10.7±0.0 ^{ab}	155.2±0.5 ^a	31.5±0.1 ^a	22.8±0.7 ^b
PLA-LAE/PLA	64.5±0.6 ^b	86.7±0.0 ^a	14.4±0.0 ^c	155.3±0.3 ^a	33.9±1.3 ^a	21.7±1.4 ^{ab}
PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1	65.1±0.1 ^b	86.9±0.7 ^a	11.2±0.1 ^{ab}	155.1±0.8 ^a	31.3±0.1 ^a	22.8±0.1 ^b

293 Lower case letters a-c indicate significant differences among samples (p<0,05) according to ANOVA analysis and Tukey's test.

294

295 PLA fibers presented a glass transition at 69 °C, a cold crystallization reordering at 93 °C,
 296 and a melting transition at 154 °C. Other works about the development of electrospun PLA
 297 fibers have presented similar thermal parameter values (Hajikhani et al., 2021; Wang et al.,
 298 2017). The incorporation of LAE into PLA fiber did not significantly affect the melting
 299 temperature and enthalpy of PLA. However, LAE significantly reduced the T_g and T_{cc} of the
 300 polymer. This result demonstrated that LAE acted as a plasticizer, which gave greater
 301 mobility to the polymer chains and caused a cold crystallization at a lower temperature.
 302 Furthermore, the incorporation of LAE molecules between the PLA chains inhibited the
 303 ordering of the polymeric chains during the fiber formation, which was evidenced by an
 304 increase of the cold crystallization enthalpy and a significant reduction of the PLA
 305 crystallinity. Previous research works found similar behavior with the incorporation of other
 306 plasticizers, such as acetyl tri-n-butyl citrate and polyethylene glycol, and certain active
 307 compounds (ungeremine, merken and natural extracts) (Baiardo et al., 2003; Llana-Ruiz-
 308 Cabello et al., 2015; López de Dicastillo et al., 2017; Moeini et al., 2020; Ozkoc &
 309 Kemaloglu, 2009).

310 DSC analysis of coaxial PLA-LAE/PLA fiber showed that the incorporation of LAE in the
311 mat's core also had a plasticizing effect. However, this plasticizer effect was less significant
312 than the effect in uniaxial PLA-LAE fiber, as it was evidenced by a lower reduction of the
313 T_g of the PLA-LAE/PLA fiber. This difference can be attributed to the fact that the
314 plasticizing effect and steric hindrance of the LAE against crystallization took place only in
315 the core of the coaxial fiber, which represented 28% of the electrospun PLA, as occurred in
316 the entire structure of PLA-LAE fiber (Table 1). Even so, the crystallinity of PLA-LAE/PLA
317 did not change significantly respect to PLA-LAE and control PLA.

318 The incorporation of the CNC in PLA (PLA-CNC1 uniaxial fiber) produced a significant
319 decrease in the T_g of the polymer, which showed that, like the LAE, these nanoparticles also
320 promoted the mobility of the polymer chains in the glass region during heating. This effect
321 suggested low interactions between the functional groups of the CNC and the PLA, in
322 agreement with FTIR analysis (Figure 2) (Sung et al., 2017). Additionally, PLA crystallinity
323 was not significantly affected; only its slight reduction and an increase of T_{cc} were observed
324 with CNC incorporation, demonstrating the absence of a nucleating effect of the
325 nanocrystals.

326 The thermal properties and crystallinity of coaxial fibers PLA-LAE/PLA and PLA-
327 LAE/PLA-CNC1 were similar, showing a plasticizing effect in both fibers respect to the
328 PLA control fiber. Nonetheless, CNC slightly increased the crystallinity of the coaxial fiber.
329 Thus, interestingly, the bionanocomposite PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 presented the thermal
330 properties and crystallinity closer to those of the PLA control fiber.

331

332 *3.4 LAE release kinetics results*

333 Figure 3 and Table 2 show the experimental data of LAE release, and K and D coefficients
334 of LAE (*see mathematic model fits in Supplemental File, Appendix B.3*).

335 K coefficients were determined when concentrations of released LAE reached the
 336 equilibrium. Table 2 shows that K values of each sample presented significant differences
 337 between simulants. The lowest K values obtained into 95% EtOH evidenced a practically
 338 total extraction of LAE from the active electrospun fibers. This result was probably due to
 339 the greater solubility of LAE into ethanol and the plasticization of PLA matrix by ethanol,
 340 generating a swelling of the electrospun mat and a greater LAE release (Alvarado et al.,
 341 2017; Patiño Vidal et al., 2021).

342 Furthermore, significant differences of K values between PLA-LAE and PLA-LAE/PLA
 343 fibers were only shown into 10% EtOH. In this food simulant, encapsulated LAE into
 344 uniaxial fiber was easily released, while in the coaxial fiber, an amount of LAE released
 345 from their core could have been retained into the shell during the diffusion process.

346
 347 **Figure 3.** Release curves of LAE to 10% EtOH (empty symbols) and 95% EtOH (filled
 348 symbols) from antimicrobial fibers: a) PLA-LAE (black circles), b) PLA-LAE/PLA (red
 349 triangles), and c) PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 (blue squares).

350 *Released LAE concentrations into the food simulants were normalized per weight of electrospun mat (0.020
 351 g). *Release data between 6-47 h followed the same equilibrium.

352

353 **Table 2.** Partition and diffusion coefficients of released LAE from electrospun fibers
354 towards food simulants.

Electrospun fiber	$K_{pm/fs}$		D ($\times 10^{-13}$) ($m^2 s^{-1}$)	
	10% EtOH	95% EtOH	10% EtOH	95% EtOH
PLA-LAE	308.9 ± 2.4^{aB}	4.5 ± 0.8^{aA}	4.7 ± 0.6^{cA}	3.1 ± 0.1^{cA}
PLA-LAE/PLA	372.4 ± 0.4^{bB}	1.9 ± 0.1^{aA}	2.7 ± 0.3^{bA}	2.4 ± 0.1^{bA}
PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1	978.7 ± 24.7^{cB}	14.7 ± 3.1^{bA}	0.8 ± 0.0^{aA}	1.3 ± 0.1^{aB}

355 Lowercase letters (a-c) indicate significant differences of a parameter between samples in the same food
356 simulant, and uppercase letters (A and B) indicate significant differences of a parameter of the same
357 sample between both simulants according to ANOVA analysis and Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$).
358

359 The incorporation of CNC into the shell produced a drastic increase in the partition
360 coefficients associated with several facts occurring during fiber obtention and LAE release
361 to food simulants. On the one hand, some hydrogen bond interactions probably occurred
362 between hydroxyl groups of CNC and carbonyl groups of PLA during the preparation of the
363 shell polymeric solution of coaxial fibers. Thus, as LAE is a big molecule, these interactions
364 inhibited the total release of LAE from the core of the coaxial PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 fiber
365 to simulants. Moreover, possible electrostatic attractions induced by ion exchange between
366 negatively charged CNC sulfate groups and positively charged LAE guanidinium groups
367 could also occur during the release assays of LAE. Thus, the antimicrobial compound was
368 partially retained in the shell of fibers. Two previous works carried out by Chi & Catchmark,
369 2017 and Silva et al., 2019 used isothermal titration calorimetry and a spectrophotometric
370 technique in order to study the LAE binding affinity towards CNC and cellulose nanofibrils
371 in an aqueous medium (ultrapure water). Interactions between the CNC or cellulose
372 nanofibrils with LAE were evidenced and associated to electrostatic attraction of their
373 charged groups. Therefore, in this work, such interactions could occur during the release of

374 LAE from electrospun bionanocomposite to 10% EtOH since this simulant exhibits a
375 behavior of an aqueous medium.

376 Regarding the diffusion behavior of LAE through the polymer matrix, theoretical and
377 experimental values were well fitted in all release kinetics LAE (*see Figure S1 in the*
378 *Supplemental File, Appendix B.3*). D values were dependent on the structure of the
379 electrospun fiber and the incorporation of CNC. Core/shell structure significantly decreased
380 the LAE release rate from fibers to the simulants. As is shown in Table S2, uniaxial and
381 coaxial fibers were composed of approx. 96 wt% PLA. The coaxial PLA-LAE/PLA fiber
382 consisted of 28 and 68 wt% PLA in the core and shell, respectively. Therefore, LAE (4.23
383 wt%) was distributed in the whole uniaxial structure and displayed a burst release to the
384 simulant. Meanwhile, the LAE encapsulated into the core of the coaxial fiber diffused from
385 the core and through the shell. Furthermore, the higher crystallinity of PLA-LAE/PLA than
386 PLA-LAE fiber could also favor a slow diffusion of LAE (Table 2).

387 Previous works of active materials have demonstrated that the diffusion process of LAE can
388 be affected by: i) the structure and the crystallinity of the material; ii) the type of polymer;
389 and iii) the interactions polymer-LAE (Patiño Vidal et al., 2021). Muriel-Galet et al. (2013)
390 indicated that LAE was slowly diffused through two ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer films
391 with different vinyl alcohol content, and caused a decrease in the crystallinity of the active
392 films (Muriel-Galet et al., 2013). Meanwhile, the slow diffusion of LAE through chitosan
393 films has been attributed to the anti-plasticizing effect through chemical interactions between
394 the polymer and the antimicrobial compound (Higuera et al., 2013). Besides, comparing D
395 values of these mentioned works (1×10^{-14} to $1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), it is highlighted that the PLA-
396 LAE and PLA-LAE/PLA fibers presented higher D values due to the fiber morphology with
397 a smaller diameter and, therefore, a higher contact area with the food simulants, and a
398 minimum chemical interaction between PLA and LAE according to FTIR analysis.

399 The incorporation of CNC in the shell of the coaxial active fiber (PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1
400 bionanocomposite) decreased D values of LAE (Table 2). This fact could be due to the
401 tortuous path in the shell caused by the good dispersion of CNC into the PLA matrix
402 (*evidenced by thermogravimetric analysis, see Supplemental File, Appendix B.4*).
403 Furthermore, an increase in the crystallinity due to the incorporation of CNC (Table 1) could
404 have also favored a slow diffusion of LAE through the shell before the release to the
405 simulants. Rojas *et al.* (2020) evidenced a similar effect when incorporated CNC into the
406 shell of active PVOH-curcumine/PLA fibers (Rojas et al., 2020). LAE release from coaxial
407 fibers displayed slightly higher D values in 95% EtOH. This fact could be related to a greater
408 plasticization of the polymeric matrix and the decrease of PLA hydrophobicity thanks to
409 CNC-PLA interactions. Therefore, encapsulated LAE into the core of fibers rapidly diffused
410 through the shell and was released to the food simulant.

411

412 *3.5 Antibacterial activity of the electrospun bionanocomposite*

413 The antibacterial activities of the electrospun PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 bionanocomposite
414 against Gram(-) and Gram(+) bacteria expressed as logarithmic reduction of cell
415 concentrations are shown in Figure 4. The experimental conditions of the assay resulted in
416 bacteria control concentrations between 1.1 and 1.4×10^8 CFU mL⁻¹. Similarly, cell growth
417 was also favored with control CNT-PLA. However, the cell concentrations were slightly
418 lower than CNT-Bacteria, resulting in log reduction values between 0.1 and 0.6. This slight
419 antimicrobial activity occurred due to minimum hydrolysis of the PLA produced at the
420 experimental conditions, which favored the presence of small molecules of lactic acid that
421 changed the pH of the medium and affected the cell growth (Ulloa et al., 2019; Villegas et
422 al., 2019).

423 The same area/volume ratio of 6 dm² L⁻¹ used in both the antibacterial and the release
 424 experiments allowed the correlation between the antibacterial activity of the electrospun
 425 bionanocomposite with the migrations assays. As is shown in Figure 4, electrospun
 426 bionanocomposite exhibited high antibacterial activities against all microorganisms, as
 427 evidenced by log cycle reduction values higher than 7 (Figure 4).

428
 429 **Figure 4.** Logarithmic reduction of Gram (-) and Gram (+) bacteria cell concentrations after
 430 contact with: CNT-Bacteria (Bacteria medium), CNT-PLA fiber and PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1
 431 nanocomposite. Lowercase letters (a-b) indicate significant differences between bacteria for
 432 the same sample according to ANOVA analysis and Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$).

433
 434 This antibacterial effectiveness was slightly higher than the values of other LAE-loaded
 435 active materials. Chitosan film loaded with 10 wt% LAE displayed a logarithmic reduction
 436 of 6 and 5 logs for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively (Higuera et al., 2013). A bilayer
 437 system composed of an extruded PLA film coated with silicone containing 2.5 wt%. LAE
 438 manifested a reduction of approx. 5 log units for *L. monocytogenes* and *S. thyphymurium*.

439
 440 **4. Conclusions**

441 An antibacterial bionanocomposite with a core/shell structure and loaded with LAE and
442 CNC was obtained through coaxial electrospinning. The incorporation of both components
443 into the coaxial fiber (PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC) improved their morphology in terms of lower
444 bead formation and homogenous diameter sizes compared to control PLA fiber. The
445 crystalline structure of PLA was slightly modified due to CNC in the shell structure.
446 Meanwhile, interactions between LAE and PLA in the core structure were verified. The
447 simultaneous incorporation of LAE and CNC into the PLA coaxial fibers did not significantly
448 modify the thermal properties and crystallinity of the polymer.
449 The release of LAE from electrospun bionanocomposite PLA-LAE/PLA-CNC1 towards an
450 aqueous and fatty simulant was significantly slowed down by the presence of the core/shell
451 structure and the CNC. Higher release of LAE was obtained in the fatty simulant compared
452 to the aqueous due to the plasticizing effect of the former in the polymer matrix. Finally,
453 high antibacterial activities were shown against Gram(+) and Gram(-) bacteria. Thus, the
454 developed electrospun bionanocomposite can be used to develop active packaging materials
455 with potential applications in fatty foods.

456

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463

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465 **Cristian Patiño Vidal:** Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation,
466 Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Eliezer Velásquez:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing -
467 Review & Editing. **María José Galotto:** Resources. **Carol López de Dicastillo:** Conceptualization,
468 Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

469

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